

Names of the Days of the Week

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INTRODUCTION

The planetary association of the days of the seven-day week is an interesting question to which there is no clear answer. Zerubavel¹ suggests that the astrological week (with the present day names) arose in Alexandria during second century BCE from where it went to Rome a century later but doesn't provide any conclusive evidence of the origins. He describes its use in Rome dismissing the idea that it could have arisen either in Babylonia or in the Jewish world. Emperor Constantine adopted the seven-day week for official use in 321 CE, making the Day of the Sun (*dies Solis*) a legal holiday. That the planetary names spread in the West in early centuries is suggested by the title of a lost essay by Plutarch (46-119) in which he wonders why the day names don't follow the order of the planets.

Latin names for the days of the week are quite like Sanskrit names. Starting with Sunday they are named after the Sun (Ravi or Āditya रवि or आदित्य), the Moon (Soma or Candra, सोम or चन्द्र), Mars (Maṅgala or Bhauma or Kuja, मङ्गल or भौम or कुज), Mercury (Budha बुध), Jupiter (Bṛhaspati or Guru, बृहस्पति or गुरु), Venus (Śukra, शुक्र), and Saturn (Śani, शनि). In short, the order of the planets for the day names is:

Sun — Moon — Mars — Mercury — Jupiter — Venus — Saturn

This is not the same as their order in the solar system, so how was the order of the planets chosen? And why are these names the same across many cultures but not in all? For example, in Greek, Arabic, Hebrew and Slavic languages they are ordered as Day One, Day Two, and so on.

Scholars have not investigated India as an alternative source of the innovation for the history of Indian astronomy has been based on the wrong premise that its foundations are to be seen in Mesopotamia. One evidence adduced for this belief is that the division of the circle into 360 parts as well as of the year into 12

parts came to India from Mesopotamia, which is false for both these are already described in the much earlier R̥gveda.² In recent decades, a more elaborate theory related to the Greek origin of a text called Yavanajātaka was advanced, but this has been refuted.³ Given there is no clarity about the origins of the week in Egypt or Mesopotamia, we explore the alternative hypothesis of its possible origin in India.

GERMANIC AND PERSIAN NAMES

In languages such as Germanic and Persian, the names of deities do not appear at first sight to correspond to the planets in the list.

In Germanic languages, Tuesday through Friday are named after the deities Týr, Ódin, Thor, and Freya, from where we get Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday, and Friday.

In Old Norse sources, Týr is described as the son of Ódin, who is Mercury (Budha in astrology is Viṣṇu). In other words, Mars (Skanda, स्कन्द, general of the devas) is viewed as son of Viṣṇu, rather than of Śiva (this variant story may be seen in the context of Skanda Upaniṣad, which tells us that Viṣṇu and Śiva are identical).

Thor in Germanic mythology is a hammer-wielding god associated with thunder, lightning, storms, oak trees, strength, the protection of mankind, and also hallowing and fertility. The Romans saw Thor as the German analog of Jupiter, and his hammer was viewed as similar to the club of Hercules. The hammer of Thor is also similar to the plough (*hala*) used as a weapon by Balarāma.

The Indo-European linguist Émile Benveniste saw Freya or Frigg as cognate with Priya, a daughter of Dakṣa, and thus a generic name of the Goddess.⁴

In Persian, the names of the days (*ruz*) starting Sunday are Mehr ruz, Māh ruz, Bahrām ruz, Tir ruz, Hormazd ruz, Nāhid ruz, and Keyvān ruz. A little bit of analysis shows that they are not really different from the Indian scheme. Mehr is Mitra, another name for Sun; Māh is Māsa which is Moon, Bahrām is derived from the earlier Verethragna that corresponds to the Sanskrit Vṛtrahana which means Mars (slayer of Vṛtra who was originally Indra but in later stories was identified with Skanda).

Tīr तीर, arrow, hearkens to the archer Arash's arrow that covers part of the globe which story is a retelling of the three steps of Viṣṇu. Some scholars see Arash, the archer Ǝrəxša (Yasht 8.6), as similar to Rudra, but I think in the identification with Mercury, the story of Viṣṇu holds more weight.

Hormazd is Ahura Mazda, the prophet-teacher of the Persians, fulfilling the role of Guru, Nāhid is from the goddess Anāhitā associated with water, fertility,

wisdom, warfare, and eventually the planet Venus, and Keyvān is Saturn. Some see Keyvān borrowed from Mesopotamia but that is not necessary since it means the greatest poet-sacrificer (*kavi*) for it was known that this planet was furthest from Earth.

Thus the evidence suggests that the names of the days were originally after deities, but after the triumphs of Christianity and Islam, certain cultures were compelled to abandon the system that to the new rulers smacked of idolatry.

The Slavic nations were victims of the Northern Crusades and they were violently separated from their old tradition.⁵ In contrast, the Germanic nations, which were Christianized more slowly, held on to the names of their deities although they also lost the deeper connection. The growth of Christianity in Southern Europe was even more gradual and the earlier names held on.

GREEK NAMES FOR THE DAYS

It is most interesting that the Greek names for the days follow the numerical system and are different from the Indian names: Κυριακή (*Kyriakí*), Δευτέρα (*Deftéra*), Τρίτη (*Tríti*), Τετάρτη (*Tetárti*), Πέμπτη (*Pémpti*), Παρασκευή (*Paraskeví*), and Σάββατο (*Sávato*). Thus Sabbath (*Savato*) is the seventh day.

There is a theory that the names for the days of the week came from Greek astrology and spread across Eurasia in the first or second century CE. But this theory is clearly wrong for it cannot explain how Rome and India across the borders of the Greek world on opposite sides have the same system, different from the Greeks.

We know that the Indians had much to say about the planets in the third millennium BCE⁶, long before the Greeks or the Babylonians⁷, and the sparsely populated Śaka corridor⁸ served as a passage for cultural diffusion from India to the Slavic world and beyond. India and Rome also had much sea trade during the imperial period and that could have served as an additional conduit for the diffusion of ideas.⁹

ORDER OF THE PLANET NAMES

The Moon, Mercury, and Venus are the inner planets, whereas Mars, Jupiter, and Saturn are the outer ones. The sidereal periods (referenced to the distant stars) are proportional to the distance from the Sun and the closer a planet is to the Sun the faster it moves. The planet names for weekdays alternate between the outer and the

inner planets. The order of the planets starting with the Sun which takes place of Earth and after the Moon going out to Saturn and then down is:

Sun — Venus — Mercury — Moon — Saturn — Jupiter — Mars

In this scheme, the two referents are the Sun with which we begin the order of the inner planets and Saturn with which we begin the order of the outer planets. According to the Padma Purāṇa, Saturn is the son of the Sun, which appears to support this assignation. (Additionally, in the Sūrya Siddhānta, Mars is born to Earth, and Mercury to Moon hence also called Saumya.)

An interesting astrological theory regarding the order chosen is described in the Sūrya Siddhānta.¹⁰ The first hour of the first day of the week was ascribed to the Sun in the series related to distance from the Earth.

Saturn — Jupiter — Mars — Sun— Venus — Mercury — Moon

The hours were thus marked to Sun, Venus, Mercury, Moon, Saturn, Jupiter, Mars. The eighth hour of the first day was ascribed again to the Sun, and also the fifteenth and twenty second; the twenty fifth hour (the first hour of the next day) is the Moon, a shift to the right of three, which mathematically is the equation $24n \text{ modulo } 7$, where n is the day count where the start is $n = 0$. Following this cycle for every hour and every day in the week, the first hours of the following days after Sunday will be ascribed to Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter and Venus, which are the familiar names of the days.

This system also assigns the planets to months and years.

*	Hours	Days	Months	Years
1	Sun	Sun	Sun	Sun
2	Venus	Moon	Mars	Mercury
3	Mercury	Mars	Jupiter	Saturn
4	Moon	Mercury	Saturn	Mars
5	Saturn	Jupiter	Moon	Venus
6	Jupiter	Venus	Mercury	Moon
7	Mars	Saturn	Venus	Jupiter

From the Sūrya Siddhānta

It is not surprising that modular mathematics was at the basis of the astronomy of altar ritual of the second millennium BCE.¹¹

FURTHER EVIDENCE FROM INDIA

The Pañcaviṃśa-Brāhmaṇa (PB),¹² which is clearly prior to Babylonian astronomical texts, speaks of division of the year into many six-day periods (ṣaḍaha), but often such six-day periods are paired with single-day counts as in 33-day rite of PB 24.2, the addition of svarasāman day in 49-day rites of PB 24.11 and PB 24.12. In PB 24.20, in the sattrā of one year also we see many 6-day periods paired with svarasāman days. There are also counts by 5-days indicating that whereas the 6-day soma-rite was the most commonly described in this Brāhmaṇa, counting by 5 and 7 was also done.

Furthermore, the number seven is associated with the Sun (whose motion orders time) in the earliest texts, as in its seven steeds and seven rays; seven sages (सप्तर्षि) are also associated with time. The number seven is associated with the earth, the body (seven dhātu), the seven steps at a marriage, the seven regions of the earth, the seven constituent parts of a kingdom, the seven stories of the palace, the seven tongues of fire, and seven musical notes.

Given the centrality of seven in the Indian imagination, and lack of evidence related to its origins elsewhere, it is likely that the division of the week into seven days occurred in India.

CONCLUSIONS

The emergence of the seven-day week with astrological names could have been a result of innovation arising out of interaction between India and the West. This interaction was not only via land for we know of the intense trade by ship between Rome and South India.¹³ It is around this period that we see evidence for the use of the seven-day week in Rome, but since our evidence is only circumstantial, it does not rule out Alexandria as the source.

If one accepts the hypothesis of the origins of the names of the days of the week in India, one can then explain the commonality of the names in India and Rome despite the use of different naming in Greece.

NOTES

1. Zerubavel (1989)
2. Kak (2003); see also Achar (2016) for the Vedic origins of the nakṣatras.
3. See Mak (2016) and Mak (2019) that shows that the singular drive to discover sources of Indian astronomy in Mesopotamia has been marred by serious errors and fabrications.
4. Benveniste (1969)
5. Kak (2020), Kak (2021)
6. Kak (1996)
7. Kak (2016)
8. Kak (2021)
9. Kak (2015); Young (2001)
10. Burgess (1860)
11. Kak (1995); It is intriguing that the use of 30 muhūrtas, instead of 24 hours, with 9 grahas (planets) also gives the same assignment for the day names. The mathematics will be $30 \pmod{9}$ and with 27 accounted for in three rounds, the next day first muhūrta will be mapped to the fourth in the list, which is Moon.
12. Caland (1931)
13. Young (2001)

REFERENCES

- B.N.N. Achar, Revisiting the calendar tradition of ancient India. *Indian Journal of History of Science* 51 (2016)
- E. Benveniste, *Indo-European language and society*, translated by Elizabeth Palmer. Faber and Faber (1973)
- E. Burgess, Translation of the *Sūrya-Siddhānta*. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 6 (1860) 141–498 (1860)
- W. Caland, *Pañcaviṃśa-Brāhmaṇa*. Asiatic Society (1931)
- S. Kak, The astronomy of the age of geometric altars. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society* 36, 385-396 (1995)
- S. Kak, Knowledge of planets in the third millennium BC. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Astronomical Society* 37, 709-715 (1996)
- S. Kak, Babylonian and Indian astronomy: early connections. *History of Science, Philosophy & Culture in Indian Civilization*, vol. 1, part 4 (A Golden Chain, G.C. Pande, ed.), pp. 847-869, 2005; arXiv:physics/0301078

- S. Kak, *The Wishing Tree* (Third Edition). Aditya Prakashan (2015)
- S. Kak, *The Astronomical Code of the Rgveda* (Third Edition). Aditya Prakashan (2016)
- S. Kak, Uttarakuru and the Slavs. *Itihas Darpan* 25, 59-66 (2020)
- S. Kak, Svetovid and Śiva. Conference on “Belarus and Cultural Legacy of Ancient Times and Middle Ages”. (2021)
- B.M. Mak, The date and nature of Sphujidhvaja’s Yavanajātaka reconsidered in the light of some newly discovered materials. *History of Science in South Asia* 1, 1-20 (2013)
- B.M. Mak, Greco-Babylonian astral science in Asia — Patterns of dissemination and transformation (East-West Encounter in the Science of Heaven and Earth 天と地の科学 — 東と西の出会い, edited by Tokimasa Takeda and Bill M. Mak) (2019)
- G.K. Young, *Rome's Eastern Trade: International Commerce and Imperial Policy, 31 BC–AD 305*. Routledge (2001)
- E. Zerubavel, *The Seven Day Circle*. University of Chicago Press (1989)